

Unlocking PV Potential in Existing Urban Settings of Prague Towards Low-Carbon Districts

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Abstract. Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) represents great potential for urban sustainability by enhancing energy savings and supporting the transition to a net-zero carbon system. This study evaluates BIPV's feasibility in existing urban structures, focusing on energy consumption and savings at the neighborhood scale under current conditions and future renovations. Analyzing five diverse urban contexts in Prague—including historical centers, modern neighborhoods, and suburbs—this research examines 100 x 100-meter sections to compare urban, architectural, and technical factors. Using meteorological data and a grid aligned with PV module dimensions, we assess solar potential through irradiation thresholds, shading effects, and available PV surfaces. Energy models for selected sites estimate PV production relative to consumption, evaluating BIPV's role in local energy needs and flexibility. This work aims to inform design and planning strategies, advancing energy-neutral, low-carbon urban districts by seamlessly integrating BIPV into the urban landscape while maintaining functional and aesthetic value in sustainable architecture.

1. Introduction

The sourcing and management of energy directly affect the environment, economy, and society. Global energy use continues to rise, while Europe's efficiency efforts have only stabilized overall demand. In line with the EU's ambition to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, electricity needs will inevitably grow, particularly if solar power expands as planned, targeting at least 600 GW of photovoltaic (PV) capacity by 2030, up from approximately 338 GW in 2024 [1]. Ground-mounted solar farms are one means to meet this demand, yet open landscapes play a crucial role in addressing the climate crisis. Notably, "*cities produce over 75 % of the world's CO₂ emissions, consume 75 % of natural resources and produce 50 % of waste – but also account for 80 % of GDP*" [2]. Thus, they hold significant potential to drive system-wide change.

Given that most of Europe's current building stock will still exist in 2050, renovation and repurposing of existing structures are vital. In Prague, for instance, 88% of the 2022 building stock is expected to remain in use [3]. Likewise, the World Green Building Council estimates that half of all buildings that will exist in 2050 are already standing today [4]. These facts underscore the importance of retrofitting and rethinking the built environment – a message echoed at the 2023 International Union of Architects (UIA) Congress in Copenhagen.

Building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) represents a significant opportunity in this context. Beyond simply generating electricity, BIPV can serve as an architectural element, ranging from unobtrusive rooftop modules that blend seamlessly with historic districts to more expressive façade solutions that can redefine building aesthetics [5]. However, effective BIPV deployment requires understanding local PV potential, energy demand, and regulatory limits.

1.1 Aim of the Study

Despite extensive large-scale studies quantifying rooftop PV capacity (e.g., ~560 GW or 680 TWh/year across the EU [6]; ~13.7 TWh/year in the Czech Republic [7]), these tend to rely on broad geospatial or statistical data [8], omit shading from adjacent buildings, or overlook aesthetic, historical, and legislative constraint – particularly in heritage zones. While national reports address technical potential, they rarely account for localized architectural sensitivities or detailed building-level data. Recent policy guidelines (e.g., the National Heritage Institute statement [9]) are also seldom integrated into technical assessments of PV feasibility. Therefore, this study aims to close this gap by:

- Conducting a detailed, location-specific analysis of PV potential for representative neighborhoods in Prague, factoring in building orientation, urban Density, shading, and heritage considerations.
- Demonstrating how BIPV can be integrated into existing building envelopes—especially in historically sensitive contexts—while respecting local architectural characteristics.
- Providing energy-demand estimates that allow direct comparison of PV production and consumption, illustrating where BIPV alone can or cannot achieve local energy neutrality.

In doing so, the study offers a more nuanced understanding of how BIPV may contribute to low-carbon, energy-resilient districts, particularly in Central European settings with diverse urban forms and strong heritage values. The results can inform practical design strategies for architects, planners, and policymakers seeking to harness solar energy potential without compromising cultural and urban quality.

2. Methods

The primary goal was to realistically evaluate Prague's PV potential, viewed as a "model" Central European city, and to assess the viability of BIPV across existing urban structures. The work was divided into four primary steps:

Step 1 – Selection of representative urban structures.

Step 2 – Urban and architectural assessment.

Step 3 – Technical assessment and PV simulation.

Step 4 – Energy balance calculation.

This approach highlights the interplay between potential PV generation, building characteristics, and cultural constraints by applying a consistent modeling framework across diverse contexts.

2.1 Urban structures

Five representative Prague neighborhoods (Figure 1) were chosen based on planning documents (Spatial Analytical Documentation [10] and the proposed Metropolitan Plan) and practical criteria such as representativeness, simulation feasibility, and main residential usage. Each typology is primarily residential, allowing similar load profiles for energy analysis.

A 100 × 100 m (1 ha) area was defined for each site, treating all buildings within it as a single zone:

01. Historic Grown Structure - Old Town: Dense medieval core (11th–20th century), UNESCO-protected, high visibility and aesthetic sensitivity.
02. Block Structure – Vinohrady: Late 19th–early 20th-century grid, high heritage value, moderate-to-high sensitivity.
03. Modernist High-Rise – Jižní Město: Prefabricated blocks (1970–1990), minimal heritage constraints, large open spaces.
04. Garden City – Hanspaulka: Planned low-rise district (1920–1940), moderate visibility, partial heritage protection.
05. Suburban Low-Rise – Křeslice: Contemporary suburb (post-2000), very low Density, minimal heritage constraints.

Figure 1. Selected sites and the analyzed part of the territory. Source of aerial photographs: IPR Prague.

2.2 Architectural, urban, and social limits

Beyond technical assessments, BIPV feasibility depends on "soft" constraints such as legislative restrictions (e.g., heritage protection), social acceptance, and aesthetic considerations. Drawing on LESO-QSV principles [11], two key factors are "sensitivity" – the degree to which changes affect architectural or historical value and "visibility" – the extent to which surfaces (roofs, façades) are seen from public viewpoints, as the two essential criteria for assessing the requirements for the degree of integration of photovoltaics (Figure 2). Historic cores thus demand more cautious integration, while modernist or suburban settings often allow more straightforward applications.

Figure 2. The adapted LESO-QSV tool, used to assess the architectural requirements for BIPV systems.

2.3 Photovoltaic potential

A detailed 3D model was created for each site using building and terrain data combined with local climatic inputs. A grid-based solar analysis was conducted utilizing ClimateStudio,

subdividing each surface into a 1×1 m grid. Areas meeting minimum irradiation thresholds (e.g., 800 kWh/m^2 for roofs, 600 kWh/m^2 for façades) were deemed suitable for BIPV. The photovoltaic potential E_{PV} was calculated as:

$$E_{PV} = \eta \times PR \times \sum_{i=1}^n (I_i \times A_i)$$

Where η is module efficiency (assumed 18%), PR is the performance ratio (0.85), I_i is incident solar radiation on the i -th area, and A_i is the corresponding surface area.

This study assumes a uniform performance ratio and does not explicitly model degradation over time. In practice, more exposed or poorly ventilated BIPV surfaces may experience higher performance losses, which should be considered in long-term assessments.

2.4 Energy Demand

Using the same 3D model, thermal (heating, cooling, hot water) and electrical (lighting and equipment) energy demands were estimated for each site. Standardized hourly consumption profiles [12] were applied to the baseline electrical energy demand (excluding heating and cooling energy). The resulting gross electricity consumption was calculated based on occupancy and floor area data. Envelope properties (thermal transmittance, fenestration ratios) were derived from typical construction assemblies and national norms (ČSN) [13]. The prefabricated houses of Jižní Město were assumed to have been renovated and insulated in the late 1990s and early 2000s, and the values were adjusted accordingly (Table 2). This approach directly compares potential PV generation and actual energy demands, illuminating where BIPV can substantially contribute to local self-sufficiency.

3. Results

3.1 Urban analysis

Each site's urban morphology, historical constraints, and visibility were examined to inform BIPV integration strategies. An adapted LESO-QSV system (Figure 3) guided the evaluation of geometry, materials, and details required for different sensitivities (e.g., heritage significance) and visibility levels (e.g., near vs. far views). Key indicators are summarized in Table 1. Old Town exhibits the highest built Footprint ($7,234 \text{ m}^2$), while Křeslice stands at $1,953 \text{ m}^2$. Jižní Město's smaller Footprint ($2,910 \text{ m}^2$) is offset by a mean of nearly 10 floors, giving it the highest overall Density (2.85). Old Town ranks second in Density (2.51), followed by Vinohrady (2.21). Hanspaulka remains under 1.0, and Křeslice is just 0.38, reflecting its low-rise suburban character. Visibility assessments considered roofs and façades separately. Old Town's dense medieval core features high near and far visibility, demanding careful aesthetic integration, whereas Jižní Město has limited roof visibility but prominent façades. Hanspaulka presents moderate sensitivity, and Křeslice, with minimal heritage considerations, offers the most flexibility for PV integration.

Figure 3. Assessment of the 5 structures using an adapted LESO-QSV system.

Table 1. Comparison of urban analysis data for the 5 typical urban structures studied.

Value	01. Old Town	02. Vinohrady	03. Jižní Město	04. Hanspaulka	05. Křeslice
Built Footprint [m ²]	7,234	4,560	2,910	3,291	1,953
Mean no. of Floors	3.47	4.85	9.80	3.01	1.97
Density ^b	2.51	2.21	2.85	0.99	0.38

^a Built-up area index = footprint/site area.

^b Density = gross floor area index (sum of gross areas of all floors/site area).

3.2 PV potential

A theoretical maximum photovoltaic potential was simulated for each 100 × 100 m site using 3D modeling of building envelopes, local terrain, and climate data (Figure 4). Values span from 657 MWh/year in the low-density Křeslice to 1,719 MWh/year in Old Town's dense historic core. Jižní Město reaches 1,606 MWh/year, Vinohrady 1,448 MWh/year, and Hanspaulka 1,184 MWh/year. These results correlate with expectations since the dense development of the city center has the largest available surface area (over 45,000 m²), almost 6 times larger than the available surface area of the development of Křeslice.

However, irradiance values above a specified threshold were considered to reach realistic results in further assessment. The determination of such a threshold is based on the expected economic payback of the system. It depends on several factors that may change significantly in the future, mainly due to higher efficiency and lower cost of available technologies, changes in the price of energy, or taking into account other requirements (e.g., using a PV panel as an element of the façade cladding will eliminate the need – and costs – of other façade materials). For the presented analyses, relatively conservative values were set: for roofs, a limit of 800 kWh/m², and for façades, 600 kWh/m². Window openings in the building envelope were also considered in the simulation based on a detailed evaluation of sample buildings in the selected areas. As shown in Table 2, Křeslice retains more than 38% of its envelope above the threshold, whereas Old Town drops below 12%. Jižní Město remains around 19%. In modernist or suburban contexts (e.g., Jižní Město, Křeslice), façades yield around 19% of the total feasible PV; in Vinohrady and Old Town, façades contribute under 7.5%.

Figure 4. 3D model of each structure with mapped solar irradiance and monthly PV potentials.

To assess the impact of orientation, we analyzed the proportion of surface areas facing different directions across the sites. A correlation analysis revealed that east-facing surfaces had the strongest positive relationship with PV potential ($r = 0.63$), while south-facing and

horizontal surfaces showed unexpectedly negative trends—likely due to shading or limited usability in dense or heritage-protected urban areas. These findings underscore the importance of orientation-aware strategies for maximizing BIPV effectiveness in both rooftops and façades.

These findings highlight the potential of façade-based systems in newer neighborhoods, while heritage-rich cores remain best suited to discreet rooftop installations. Taking also into account the urban and architectural characteristics of the buildings, it can be clearly stated that, for example, in housing estates, it makes sense to work also with the facades and to use the possibilities of BIPV in the revitalization of prefabricated houses: panels can be applied between windows, as balcony and loggia railings, but also as a full-fledged facade cladding (ventilated facade). In the case of the structures of Old Town and Vinohrady, it is obvious that in the case of BIPV application, it is necessary to concentrate mainly on the roof cladding and very carefully choose fully integrated elements with appropriate color, texture, detail, and – above all – scale.

Figure 5. Graphical representation of monthly PV potentials for the analyzed urban structures.

3.3 Energy demand

Monthly energy demand was modeled for heating, cooling, domestic hot water, lighting, and equipment (Figure 6). The electricity demand for lighting, domestic hot water, and equipment operation is practically constant throughout the year; only the electricity demand for lighting logically increases slightly in central European conditions during the winter months. However, it varies during the day, depending on the function and the number of users, but remains almost independent of external influences. This variability in demand has a major impact on the energy load matching, i.e., balancing consumption and maximum production times. Consumption can be well predicted according to typical hourly usage profiles, and generation, storage and/or energy sharing can be adapted accordingly. Conversely, the demand for cooling, especially heating, is almost constant during the day. Still, it varies considerably throughout the year depending on the climatic conditions, i.e., the outside temperature and sunshine, which influence buildings' heat losses and gains.

Old Town's older, dense construction results in an annual requirement of approximately 6,108 MWh per hectare. Vinohrady follows at 3,926 MWh/ha, while Jižní Město and Hanspaulka each approach 2,500–2,600 MWh/ha. Křeslice's low-density, modern housing consumes only ~360 MWh/ha annually.

Figure 6. Graphical representation of monthly energy needs for the analyzed urban structures.

Table 2 compares each site's real PV potential and energy demands. Křeslice emerges as the only location where annual PV potential (388 MWh/ha) exceeds total consumption (361 MWh/ha), implying a theoretical self-sufficiency of 108%. Old Town's coverage rate remains about 14%, whereas the other three sites range from 16% to 20%. These results confirm that dense heritage districts can only partly offset their energy needs through on-site photovoltaics. In contrast, modernist and suburban settings allow for more extensive PV integration and, in certain cases, near or total self-sufficiency.

Table 2. Comparison of technical data, PV potential, and energy needs analysis results for the five typical urban structures studied.

Value	01. Old Town	02. Vinohrady	03. Jižní Město	04. Hanspaulka	05. Křeslice
Mean Fenestration Ratio	0.18	0.15	0.25	0.15	0.19
Envelope Uvalue [Wm^2K^{-1}]	1.35	1.40	0.85	1.40	0.57
Total Available Surface [m^2]	45,450	28,496	16,657	17,479	6,551
Maximum PV potential [MWh]	1,719	1,448	1,606	1,184	657
Real PV potential ^a [MWh]	842	635	508	489	388
Roof Contribution [%]	92.60	92.60	81.60	81.00	81.40
PV performance ^b [kWh/m^2]	18.52	22.28	30.49	28.00	59.18
Total Energy Needs ^c [MWh]	6,108	3,926	2,596	2,404	361
PV / Energy ratio	0.14	0.16	0.20	0.20	1.08

^a Real PV potential = annual PV potential, taking into account irradiance thresholds of 600 kWh/m^2 for facades and 800 kWh/m^2 for roofs.

^b Effective PV performance = ratio of real PV potential to total available surface.

^c Total Energy Needs = annual energy needs for Heating, Cooling, DHW, Lighting, and Equipment.

4. Conclusion

Building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) offer strong potential for advancing urban sustainability while preserving architectural and cultural value. In historically sensitive districts like Prague's UNESCO-protected core, BIPV must be carefully integrated, using solutions such as roof tiles, photosensitive renders, transparent PV cells, or facade coatings that minimize visual impact. In contrast, modernist estates and post-war housing blocks offer greater design flexibility, with opportunities for flat-roof systems, PV balconies, and full-scale façade cladding.

Our results confirm that site-specific factors, particularly orientation, shading, and surface usability, strongly influence PV potential. Correlation analysis showed east-facing surfaces had the highest positive relationship, while south-facing and horizontal surfaces underperformed, likely due to dense urban shading. These findings, while insightful, are based on a limited sample and should be interpreted cautiously.

Broader systemic challenges also persist. Seasonal mismatch between summer generation and winter heating demand cannot be resolved through BIPV alone, and outdated electrical infrastructure in older districts may limit viable deployment. These limitations highlight the need to combine building-scale interventions with district-level planning and smart-grid strategies.

Despite these challenges, BIPV remains a key enabler in both new construction and retrofitting. When designed in harmony with urban morphology, supported by policy, and embedded in broader energy systems, BIPV can meaningfully contribute to the transition toward energy-resilient, low-carbon cities.

BIPV, when thoughtfully integrated, can redefine both the energy performance and the visual identity of urban architecture, contributing to a more resilient and aesthetically cohesive built environment.

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